

Ray Adaptive Stochastic Transport (RASTr) Computational Performance Trade-offs on GPU Hardware

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the implementation and performance of a new GPU-based Method of Characteristics (MOC) neutron transport solver that relies on The Random Ray Method (TRRM). Ray Adaptive Stochastic Transport (RASTr) allows for arbitrary biasing of the ray sampling distribution to provide variance reduction in problems where importance sampling is advantageous by reducing the cumulative active ray length. Additionally, the suitability of RASTr to GPU execution is enhanced due to its use of segment-uniform distributions, where each ray is guaranteed the same number of segments and stream compaction is eliminated. However, the RASTr method comes with a substantial computational penalty which in the worst case can double the amount of ray tracing operations required for the solver. This work aims to characterize the resulting problem dependent computational trade-off, providing a high level understanding of the RASTr algorithm in comparison to existing TRRM methods. The RASTr algorithm is compared to TRRM using projected kernel timing results obtained from profiling. Results identify that RASTr is preferred in problems requiring highly accurate results over a portion of the domain (i.e. benefiting from biased sampling) and having a large number of energy groups to offset the extra ray tracing operations.

Keywords: Random ray, method of characteristics, GPU

1. INTRODUCTION

Method of Characteristics (MOC) neutron transport solvers lend themselves naturally to GPU computing due to the uniformity of processes on their data [1, 2]. Ray Adaptive Stochastic Transport (RASTr) [3], an extension of The Random Ray Method (TRRM) for characteristics transport [4], allows for arbitrary biasing of the ray sampling distribution for variance reduction in problems where importance sampling is advantageous. The computational profile of RASTr differs from that of TRRM in two main respects due to the requirements for computing ray weights. First, computing ray weights requires additional ray tracing and a new weight calculation operation [3]. Secondly, the structure of the RASTr kernel is simplified relative to TRRM due to the ability to constrain ray lengths to a uniform number of segments, or “segment-uniform” distribution. The number of ray segments traced before termination in RASTr is entirely deterministic, so despite random data and random sampling, all random processes are eliminated from the GPU. This circumvents the need for a stream compaction process to maintain efficiency under stochastic ray termination conditions [5]. These differences arise from the RASTr “coverage calculation” which provides the analytical solution for the weights of rays traced on an arbitrary, angularly and spatially dependent sampling distribution. The computational benefits of variance reduction form a trade-off with the additional statistical weight calculation cost so that the choice of optimal method is problem dependent, which is described in section 3.

This work aims to characterize the resulting problem dependent computational trade-off, providing a high level understanding of the RASTr algorithm performance in comparison to existing TRRM implementations on GPU hardware. The core components of the RASTr algorithm are presented and

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compared with TRRM for GPU architectures, with key differences resulting from the segment-uniform distribution [3]. Profiling of the core RASTr kernels is performed for an existing RASTr implementation. The relative performance of the RASTr algorithm against TRRM is projected using kernel timing results to inform the idealized computational costs of TRRM.

The study is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief review of TRRM and RASTr with discussion of existing TRRM GPU methods. Section 3 provides a description of GPU considerations for the core algorithms of RASTr. A performance model is formulated to compare the performance of RASTr with TRRM and Immortal Ray as a function of the problem configuration. Section 4 presents profiling results of each core operation in a RASTr implementation and projects the relative performance of each method using the models formulated in Section 3. Conclusions are drawn in Section 5.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. The Random Ray Method of Characteristics

MOC solves the neutron transport equation using a mesh discretization in space combined with the discretization of the angular flux on characteristics, or rays. The transport equation may be represented as,

$$\hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}) + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}) = q(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega}), \quad (1)$$

where $q(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega})$ contains the cell-wise fission and scattering sources, $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \hat{\Omega})$ is the angular flux at position \mathbf{r} , energy E , direction $\hat{\Omega}$, with total macroscopic cross-section $\Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E)$. A discrete set of rays, or ray distribution, is chosen so that each ray, $\mathbf{r} \in \mathbf{r}_0 + s' \cdot \hat{\Omega} \forall 0 < s' < \ell_a$, is defined by \mathbf{r}_0 , $\hat{\Omega}$, and ℓ_a , which represent the starting position and angle, and active length respectively. The gradient operator on this ray is transformed as, $\hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi = d\psi/ds$. The characteristics based transport equation solution is defined as a collection of ordinary differential equations on characteristic rays,

$$\frac{d\psi(s, \hat{\Omega}, E)}{ds} + \Sigma_t(s, E) \psi(s, \hat{\Omega}, E) = q(s, \hat{\Omega}, E), \quad (2)$$

where each ray calculates a valid angular flux from the point-wise fields on the spatial discretization [6]. The domain is decomposed into discrete volumes such that path lengths are computed through each cell, enabling the evaluation of volume and surface integrals using the ray discretization [7]. The angular flux integration can then be solved analytically. This study considers the flat source solution where cross sections and source terms are considered constant within cells,

$$\Delta\psi_{k,g} = \left(\psi_{k,g}(s') - \frac{q_{i,g}}{\Sigma_{i,g}^T} \right) \left(1 - e^{-\Sigma_{i,g}^T \ell_k} \right), \quad (3)$$

where k is the ray index, i is the cell index, g is the energy group index, and $\ell_{k,j}$ is the path length through the cell.

The angular flux is integrated over position and angle to provide the scalar flux, which is used to calculate reaction rates. This integration requires a weighting coefficient dependent on the distribution of rays. Non-uniform quadratures of various formulations have been used since the earliest days of MOC. However, these are distinct from RASTr in that they vary only angularly. Variations in the angular quadrature may be generalized as a non-uniform sampling distribution in angle, $g(\hat{\Omega})$, where ray weights, $w(\hat{\Omega})$, are obtained relative to the solid sphere and are spatially independent. However, spatial variation in the sampling distribution, $g(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega})$, requires a more involved calculation to obtain spatially dependent weights, $w(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega})$ [3]. The general solution for the angular flux quadrature considers that ray weights may be a function of both position and angle,

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{4\pi} d\hat{\Omega} \cdot w(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) \psi(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}), \quad (4)$$

so that integration over the local volume yields,

$$\phi_i \approx \frac{4\pi \sum_{k \in V_i} w_{j,k} \ell_{j,k} \bar{\Psi}_{j,k,g}}{\sum_{k \in V_i} w_{j,k} \ell_{j,k}}, \quad (5)$$

which is defined for azimuthal and polar weights such that the ray segments at segment index j occupy a known physical width in the cell and occupy a known portion of the spherical solid angle for each ray k to integrate the average angular flux $\bar{\Psi}_{j,k,g}$ over the segment length in the area A of cell i [6].

TRRM takes advantage of the spatially and angularly uniform ray distribution to set all ray weights equal to one another thereby removing them from the equation. Given that the random rays are uniformly distributed, all rays in the distribution are weighted equally so that the scalar flux integration weights are removed from the equation.

2.1.1. Stream Compaction

TRRM relies on rays of uniform length to produce uniform ray distributions, meaning that rays may be sampled and terminated within cells, and may have a non-deterministic number of segments within each ray. Therefore, the distribution of ray segment counts is non-uniform and problem dependent [5]. When ray distributions have non-uniform numbers of segments, the data in the buffer being operated on changes randomly leading to unsorted random processes which are more costly to handle on SIMD architectures. A SIMD method of stream compaction ray buffering for handling stochastic thread termination has been implemented to rectify this issue [5].

Ray termination in a length-uniform ray distribution of TRRM is stochastic, meaning that the work assigned to each thread of a GPU device terminates in an unordered way. Each terminated ray remaining in the ray buffer is wasted compute, as no operations may be performed on it. Therefore, rays must be sorted out of the buffer and re-sampled periodically to maintain performance. Stream compaction is highly effective in eliminating the negative performance effects of non-uniform ray distributions [5, 8].

2.2. RASTr

Ray Adaptive Stochastic Transport (RASTr) requires statistical weights based on the local angular ray density to retain balance in the scalar flux integration [3]. Given that the ray weights are calculated from the local angular ray density, or angular “coverage,” any ray beginning or terminating inside of a cell contributes to a non-constant ray weight across the angular flux integration. Non-constant ray weights significantly increase both the computational cost and complexity of the angular flux solution as a whole. Therefore, it is significantly more advantageous to constrain rays such that they are only sampled and terminated at cell faces. These rays can be further constrained to have equal numbers of segments through which they have traversed, yielding the much more computationally tractable segment-uniform ray distribution [3].

RASTr solves for ray weights by performing the analytical convolution of the ray sampling distribution with the ray kernel, which can be solved as a simple stepwise solution when the sampling distribution is projected to element faces and is segment-uniform. The discrete coverage solution is then,

$$\Delta c_k = g_i^+ \ell_{j,k}^+ - g_i^- \ell_{j,k}^- \quad , \quad (6)$$

for ray k at segment j in cell i with path lengths ℓ and sampling distribution g . Δc_k , the step-wise change in ray coverage, may be solved at each segment to obtain a boundary condition and coverage solution

for the active segments [3]. The pick-up and drop-off regions, which are a consequence of the differential angular convolution solution necessary to obtain the ray weights, are indicated by + and - respectively [3]. The coverage is inverted to produce statistical weights for each ray segment, $w_{j,k} =: 1/c_{j,k}$ which are used in the scalar flux integration of Equation 5. The necessary coverage boundary condition is produced by integrating the coverage dead-zone with the pick-up term only, which accounts for the coverage contribution by rays terminating in the first active segment of the current ray.

In contrast to length-uniform ray distributions, segment-uniform ray distributions contain rays of arbitrary length, depending on the mesh and number of active segments, with weights correcting for their spatial and angular non-uniformity. As a consequence, all rays in the distribution are guaranteed to begin and terminate at the same computational step.

RASTr constrains the number of segments in the ray distribution to be uniform over all steps, which allows for deterministic access to the region in which terminating rays were sampled, g_i^- , n_a segments behind the current position. As a result, no dynamic ray buffering and resampling is required. This is computationally advantageous for thread occupancy and also allows for more efficient parallel resampling of all rays on the GPU simultaneously.

However, this presents problems for meshes with large regions of inconsistent mesh sizes. If rays travel significantly different distances, then the dead-zone of the rays is required to be the number of segments that covers the appropriate range for the given problem. This effect is problem dependent and will be ignored for the purposes of this analysis as it does not have a significant impact for problems with roughly uniform regional cell size distributions. In problems with significantly different cell sizes in different regions of the mesh, the dead-zone will have wasted compute in the regions with larger cells.

3. METHODS

After initial setup, all iterations of the RASTr algorithm are performed without large memory transfers off of the GPU beyond vector norms, variances, and entropies. There are extraneous computational costs not considered in the performance model such as the source calculation, the cost of ray sampling, convergence checking, k-eff calculation, flux normalization, etc. However, these costs are negligible or equivalent between methods and will be ignored for the purposes of relative performance comparison. For the purposes of performance modeling, it is always assumed that the GPU threads are saturated so that the compute time is directly proportional to the work given.

3.1. Performance Model Formulation

This study aims to formulate a generalized performance model which can be used to evaluate the fitness of each method for a unique problem, device, and implementation. The computational cost of RASTr can be formulated as the combined cost of its three core kernels: 1) ray tracing, 2) angular flux integration, and 3) coverage integration [3]. The first two kernels are identical between RASTr and TRRM. The last is unique to RASTr.

Figure 1. Segment and operation requirements for various solver types.

Figure 1 depicts the ray segments of each solver and the kernels that operate on each of them. n_a number of active segments are defined for each ray ahead of each sampling point to the right. n_d number of dead-zone segments are defined behind each ray to acquire the angular flux boundary condition with the exception of Immortal Ray, which uses the angular flux from the previous iteration. n_a segments are defined behind the sampling point, making up the RASTr coverage dead-zone which acquires the angular ray weight boundary condition. Consider that each solver has ray tracing and angular flux integration kernels for each of its segments, except in the extra coverage dead-zone which has no angular flux integration.

Given the assumption that the device is saturated, the computational cost of each kernel can be characterized in terms of the clock time of the kernel over the total number of segments being operated on. The ray can be expanded along a vertical axis representing the computational cost of each operation on each segment.

Figure 2. RASTr computational costs illustration.

Figure 2 depicts the computational work of each operation by the segments it operates on (x-axis) and the computational cost of the operation on each of those segments (y-axis). The area of each region represents the total clock time for that operation. g is the number of energy groups. α , β , γ are the computational costs in time per segment of the angular flux integration, ray tracing, and coverage integration kernels respectively. These are device and implementation dependent, but are fixed across varying problem configurations. Note that the computational cost of the angular flux integration is dependent on the number of energy groups.

Given a certain implementation with fixed kernel costs, three variables form the computational trade-off to determine the optimal method for a given problem. First, the ray “reduction factor,” RF , represents the factor by which the total number of active ray segments can be reduced using variance reduction. Second, the number of energy groups, g , impacts the relative cost of the angular flux integration against the ray tracing and coverage integration overhead. The cost of the additional ray tracing and coverage calculation in RASTr is amortized as the number of energy groups increases. Finally, the dead-zone fraction, $d = n_d/n_a$, is defined as the length of the dead-zone relative to the active length of the ray. The dead-zone fraction impacts the amount of additional angular flux integrations RASTr requires relative to Immortal Ray.

The cost of iterating an entire ray distribution can now be defined in terms of the parameters in Figure 2. The number of total active segments in the entire ray distribution can be defined as $N_a = rn_a$ where r is the number of rays in the distribution. For the purposes of this study, it is conservatively assumed that the stream compaction process operates perfectly, meaning that all threads operate with complete occupancy and no losses are attributed to threads going unoccupied between thread compaction processes. Additionally, this comparison implicitly assumes that the distribution of segment path lengths is approximately equal between the segment-uniform and length-uniform cases so that both methods

have approximately equal ray coverage contribution for the same computational work. The clock time, T_{RASTr} , of each iteration of RASTr is then, $T_{RASTr} = \alpha(g) (N_a + N_d) + 2\beta N_a + 2\gamma N_a$, where α is taken as a function of the energy group number g . Given that TRRM and Immortal Ray are composed of the same operations, performance comparisons can be drawn by applying the kernel costs to the required operations for each method. The idealized computational cost of TRRM has equivalent kernel costs in different proportions, $T_{TRRM} = \alpha(g) (N_a + N_d) + \beta (N_a + N_d)$. Finally, the Immortal Ray implementation discards the cost of the dead-zone completely by taking advantage of the angular flux obtained at the last iteration [5], $T_{IR} = \alpha(g) N_a + \beta N_a$. Given that Immortal Ray always has fewer operations than TRRM, RASTr is optimal when, $T_{RASTr} < RF \cdot T_{IR}$, or,

$$\alpha(g) (1 + d - RF) + (2 - RF) \beta + 2\gamma < 0, \quad (7)$$

where $d = N_d/N_a$ is defined as the dead-zone fraction, or fraction of the active ray length required for the dead-zone.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

GPU results are obtained by profiling each kernel on the C5G7 benchmark geometry with an arbitrarily modified material to adjust the number of energy groups. The performance results are only dependent on the problem formulation and geometry in the sense that they change the necessary length of the dead-zone. However, the kernel performance is problem invariant.

4.1. Device Performance Comparisons

A current RASTr implementation is profiled to obtain parameters for the cost per segment of core ray operations on each device. Several GPU devices are tested against a single CPU core (AMD Ryzen 9 5950X). Profiling across devices is to demonstrate the hardware universality of the algorithm and performance model, not to provide guidance on choice of hardware architecture. However, ideal CPU scaling may be assumed in a shared memory multi-threading case. Profiling was performed for several group structures.

Figure 3. Kernel execution shares for tested devices, $g = 7$.

Figure 4. Kernel share as a function of group number, NVIDIA 3060.

Figure 3 shows the cost per segment of each core ray kernel for a saturated ray distribution in nanoseconds per segment profiled for several devices. In general, the angular flux integration has better speedup than the coverage and ray tracing operations due to their greater compute intensity relative to the required memory transfers. However, the runtime of the coverage operation is relatively small

relative to the other components. Additionally, the work related to angular flux integration increases with the additional number of groups.

4.2. Methods Relative Performance Projection

The profiling results in Section 4.1 are used as parameters for the general performance model derived in Section 3.1 as a demonstration of the performance comparison. Relative kernel performances may vary between implementations. However, it is observed that the trends of the performance regions remain approximately equivalent across all tested devices. This can be used to determine which of the considered methods is computationally optimal for a given problem.

Figure 5. Performance comparison of methods as a function of energy groups, $RF = 1.95$, $d = 0.3$, NVIDIA 3060.

Figure 6. Optimal method regions with relative % speedup contours over alternative method as a function of problem configuration, $d = 0.3$, NVIDIA 3060.

Figure 5 shows the computational cost of each method as a function of the number of energy groups, holding the reduction factor fixed. For an assumed reduction factor of $RF = 1.95$, the relative cost of the angular flux integration changes as the number of energy groups changes. If the reduction factor is greater than one, fewer rays are traced despite having the same number of groups resulting in decreased computational work. Figure 5 can be expanded as a function of the reduction factor to yield Figure 6. As the reduction factor increases, the slope of the RASTr cost contour decreases relative to that of TRRM. Given the kernel costs for a specific device and implementation, regions can be drawn depicting the optimal choice of method for all possible problem configurations.

As the number of energy groups increases, the relative cost of the ray tracing and coverage integration of that ray is amortized as the angular flux integration makes up a greater portion of the overall compute. It is assumed that the group structure does not significantly impact the problem convergence due to the availability of acceleration methods [2, 9]. In any case, this cost is identical across the methods considered here. The cost intersection line of RASTr and Immortal Ray approaches an asymptote as the number of energy groups tends toward infinity because the relative cost of ray tracing operations approaches zero and only the difference in the number of angular flux integrations results in a computational disadvantage of RASTr. However, the cost of imperfect occupancy and stream compaction

in Immortal Ray is idealized in this study so that the relative performance of RASTr may be better in practice. This asymptote is a function of the dead-zone factor and kernel costs. Figure 5 and Figure 6 assume a dead-zone factor $d = n_d/n_a = 0.3$ for the fraction of an active ray length dedicated to the dead-zone.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The importance sampling capability of RASTr provides an implementation dependent and problem dependent performance advantage. This study provides the tools to determine under what conditions the use of RASTr is appropriate by direct profiling and performance modeling of the methods in question. While kernel performance and computational work are device and problem dependent, a general trend is characterized where RASTr is strongly preferred in problems benefiting from biased sampling and having an relatively high number of energy groups.

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